

STUDY ON EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION IDEAS CONCEPTS AND PRACTICES IN BIG DATA

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Abstract

This is an investigation into the theories, philosophies, and practices that underpin early childhood education, and it is based on a substantial quantity of evidence. This study investigates the ways in which early childhood education programmes collect and use data, the ways in which these programmes would like to use data, the ways in which these programmes could use the data that they already have, and the challenges that these programmes face in their efforts to collect and use data. Early childhood education programmes encounter a number of obstacles, one of which is that data analysis collects information in a quantitative manner (how many?), and then organizes it in some way that enables comparison and generalization possible. The purpose of this research is to analyse the data collection and utilization practices of early childhood education programmes. Program A is a private organisation that operates on a not-for-profit basis and provided services to children during their early childhood years, beginning while the children were still infants and continuing through kindergarten. There are a total of six locations where Program B, an early childhood education programme that is funded by the federal government, may be found inside the study city. In total, there were one hundred children and all forty preschool teachers included in the sample.

Keywords: Early, childhood, education, big data.

Introduction

From the 21st to the 23rd of February 2019, the Second International Biennial Conference on Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) was held at the International Conference Center in Victoria, Seychelles. The Early Childhood Care and Education Association (ECCE Association) was the one in charge of organising the conference. This event, which was a symposium, was organised in collaboration between the International Bureau of Education (IBE) of UNESCO and the Seychelles Institute of Early Childhood Development (IECD). The conference, which was held in 23 different countries and was titled "Big Data for Small Children: Monitoring Holistic Early Childhood Development," brought together approximately 340 members of various international governments, non-governmental organisations, international development agencies, and international specialists. "Big Data for Small Children: Monitoring Holistic Early Childhood Development" was the title of the conference."

This conference came just two years after the First International Biennial Conference on ECCE, which was also held in the Republic of Seychelles two years before this conference. This conference followed closely on the heels of that event. The Republic of Seychelles played home to both of the aforementioned gatherings. The relevance of adopting practical actions for each UNESCO Member State (MS) to adopt a comprehensive and multisectoral, holistic approach to ECCE emerged as the most frequent topic discussed at the 2017 conference. This was also the topic that received the most attention. During the course of the conference, attendees continued to broach this subject in their conversations.

The conference was held in the year 2017 for the first time. It is necessary to defragment, coordinate, and systematise the services that are the responsibility of multiple government departments, private organisations, and non-governmental organisations in order to take a holistic approach to early childhood care and education (ECCE). ECCE is an acronym that stands for early childhood care and education. These services include Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE), which stands for Early Childhood Development (NGOs). After the UNESCO World Congress on ECCE was held in Moscow in the year 2010, advocates for holistic approaches that arrange ECCE services have become a common fixture in the literature and discourse on ECCE practises. This event took place in the year 2010. In the time that has transpired since that happened, this has become even more abundantly clear to everyone. Following in the footsteps of its forerunner, the First International Biennial Conference on Early Childhood Care and Education, which took place in 2017, the Second International Biennial Conference on Early Childhood Care and Education, which took place in 2018, shifted its focus from advocacy to practical strategies for building holistic and resilient early childhood care and education (ECCE) systems as well as highlighting exemplars of such systems that other member states have implemented. In other words, this conference followed in the footsteps of its predecessor, the First International Biennial Conference on Early Childhood Care and This was done so that it would be similar to its predecessor from 2017, which came out in 2017.

In point of fact, managing the enormous data difficulties that are present across all of the ECCE system components is the most important practical issue that national governments (MSs) need to overcome in order to develop long-lasting and successful ECCE systems. This is because these difficulties are present across all of the ECCE system components. Inadequacies in data collection and management have been a persistent impediment to development efforts in low-income nations all over the world, as well as to ECCE initiatives globally across all levels of national income more generally, with the exception of a select few country contexts. These inadequacies have been compounded by the fact that a few countries have unique circumstances. The organizational dispersion of services, which is and will continue to be a distinguishing element of the ECCE in the vast majority of Member States, is rendered worse due to these inadequacies. This is the case because these problems make the situation worse. At the most recent conference, which was held every two years, this time-sensitive and essential subject was dissected in great detail.

The need to provide professional training and support in big data management across all stakeholder groups, to continually share and incorporate sound and successful practices, and to understand that the transition to effective big data systems in ECCE monitoring requires constant attention on decisions – that is, every step of the data organizational process – was one of the consistent themes that emerged during the framework discussions and presentations of exemplar systems. Another consistent theme that emerged was the necessity to understand that the transition to effective big data systems in ECCE monitoring requires understanding that the transition to effective big Several of the speakers went through what is commonly referred to as the "Four Vs"

of big data, which are volume, velocity, variety, and veracity respectively. It is of the utmost importance that all of these "Vs" be understood and coordinated across all ECCE frameworks and sectors.

What is early childhood education?

The phrase "early childhood education" refers to both structured and unstructured educational programmes that are offered to children from birth through the end of their preschool years in order to foster healthy growth and development (birth to age five). Children of these ages are wholly reliant on the adult caregivers in their lives, which may include their parents, daycare workers, babysitters, members of their extended families, instructors, and others.

Before a kid enters kindergarten, early childhood education (ECE) engages them in a wide range of activities that are intended to foster their intellectual and social development. Some programmes provide a primary emphasis on being prepared for school and academics, while others take a "whole kid" approach that places more of an emphasis on being mentally and emotionally prepared.

According to Dr. Negussie, one of the challenges that educators in early childhood education confront is the fact that their work is sometimes ignored or devalued as "just playing." This assertion could not be further from the reality.

She explains that many people have the wrong idea about what early childhood educators actually do. "Frequently, those who have a stake in the matter, such as parents, members of the community, and even other educators, have the mindset that whatever occurs in preschool is irrelevant because learning doesn't officially begin until the child enters kindergarten."

Young infants have minds that are very absorbent and malleable, and they are continuously learning through the interactions and experiences they have with others as well as the knowledge that is absorbed from their surroundings. They are hardwired to perceive, imitate, experiment, and explore, and they are born with the desire to learn.

What is the purpose of early childhood education?

ECE is designed to do one thing, and that is to teach children strategies that will assist them in developing the cognitive, social, and emotional abilities necessary to become learners who will continue to grow throughout their lives. According to research conducted by the Zero to Three Foundation, the following competencies should be mastered by young students as soon as possible:

Literacy and language go hand in hand; language serves as the basis for the development of reading and writing abilities. A child's enthusiasm in books and reading, as well as their eventual comprehension of these activities, can be increased by teaching them to communicate using gestures, noises, and words.

Children are born with a natural curiosity about the world around them and an urge to figure out how things function. They apply and acquire a grasp of mathematical concepts, like as counting and sorting, as well as problem-solving skills that they will need for school through their everyday experiences. Those skills will be necessary for school.

Self-control, also known as the ability to appropriately express and manage one's emotions, is necessary not just for academic achievement but also for general healthy development. Self-control can be defined as the ability to express and manage one's feelings in an appropriate manner. Children are given the ability to work with others, deal with frustration, and settle disagreements as a result of this.

Children are more eager to take on new problems when they have self-confidence because it gives them the sense that they are capable and that they believe in themselves. The ability to navigate social problems, such as sharing, competing, and making new friends, successfully requires a healthy dose of self-assurance as well.

Big data Early childhood

Early childhood data can be used to better understand the developmental requirements of early children; to guide instruction, programmes, and policies; and to identify areas in which children and families may require additional supports. A comprehensive selection of digital cameras, such as webcams, wireless cameras, digital still cameras, cameras built into smart phones, and cameras built into tablet computers. Whiteboards that are interactive and can portray children's experiences in a hurry. Audio recorders, Using presentation software like Microsoft PowerPoint on a computer to communicate one's educational experiences. The term "data analysis"

conjures up images of complex charts and graphs, computers, and other high-level methods of evaluating numerical information in the minds of many educators who work with young children.

The term "data analysis" conjures up images of complex charts and graphs, computers, and other high-level methods of evaluating numerical information in the minds of many educators who work with young children. Making a list of items and writing how many you have of each in parentheses is an example of a very simple data analysis method. Another example is creating and discussing a bar graph in which the bars are higher for snowy than rainy days in the month of January. Other teachers are aware that data analysis can be very simple. Data analysis collects information in a quantitative manner (how many?), and then organizes it in some way that makes comparison and generalization possible. This is true regardless of whether the process employs specialized statistical software or markers and chart paper.

Massive amounts of data bring both enormous potential and obstacles.

"Analogous to what it must have been like when they first handed out microscopes to microbiologists, social scientists are getting to the point in many areas where enough information exists to understand and address major previously intractable problems that affect human society," according to one theory.

Early childhood experiences are widely acknowledged to be formative for later academic success. Even while I am certain that there are some individuals who are not convinced, the fact that this hypothesis is supported by decades of research renders that irrelevant. It is one of the few things in schooling on which I would be willing to wager all of my savings for the rest of my life. Continue reading if you are curious about the importance of early childhood education as a stepping stone to later learning. In this section, we are going to talk about six early childhood ideas that serve as the cornerstone for later education.

1. **Adaption.** The capacity of a youngster to adapt a skill to the circumstances of a given situation. The highest level of achievement that may be attained in early life is adaptation. If a child learns to master this skill during their foundational years, it will only become heightened throughout the rest of their life, leading to increased skill and knowledge acquisition. If a child does not learn to master this skill during their foundational years, it will not become heightened throughout their life.
2. **Temperament.** The characteristics of your child's personality that make up their temperament will, in the long run, have an effect on their entire personality. Positive aspects of a person's personality, such as resiliency and curiosity, begin to take shape throughout the early years of childhood. Because they help kids learn at exponentially faster rates, these characteristics have the potential to play a significant part in the future.
3. **Socialization.** The capacity to learn and behave in accordance with a society's social conventions and expectations. Without the ability to interact with other people, our learning potential is severely constrained. Think about all of the things that we pick up from other people, whether they be family members, friends, classmates, instructors, mentors, or any other kind of role model you can think of. If we did not learn how to interact with others when we were young, it is likely that our skill set and the amount of information that we know would be greatly reduced.
4. **Emotional intelligence.** The expressing, comprehending, and controlling of one's emotional states. Early childhood education is where we first learn how to create the intrapersonal and interpersonal abilities necessary to participate in a learning environment and in the world in general. This skill helps us to form the skills that are required to participate in the world.
5. **Communication rules.** Rules that must be followed and traits that must be exhibited throughout a discussion in order for there to be order in the exchange. If these guidelines are not followed, there will be a breakdown in communication. Because we would be breaking the fundamental norms of communication, we would not be able to learn anything from having talks with other people because the conversation would either end or become unproductive.
6. **Imagery.** A technique for learning new information in which the youngster superimposes images of one or more stimuli on top of one other such that the relationship between the visuals assists in recalling the information. If we didn't have this ability, we wouldn't have the spatial awareness required to participate in sports or operate a vehicle.

OBJECTIVE

1. To Study on early childhood education
2. To Study on Ideas concepts and practices in big data

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Following the recommendation of the state commissioner and taking into account the availability of data to carry out example analyses, the research team contacted four of the largest programmes in the city that was the focus of the study. Two of the programmes consented to take part in the study.

Program A was a non-profit, private organisation that served children in their early childhood years, beginning when they were infants and continuing through kindergarten. Children participated in the program me for an average of eight hours each day, and it was available to them throughout the entire year. This initiative was made possible by the state, which provided funding in the form of early education slots, vouchers, and many other subsidies. Program B was an early education programme that was supported by the federal government and had six facilities located in the study city. It provided families who satisfied the income eligibility standards with early childhood education programmes for a half-day, all year long, at no cost to the families, and it also provided a full-day alternative on a sliding fee scale.

SAMPLE

The investigation focused on a single city, and the sample included all twenty preschool teachers from that city as well as fifty children (aged 3 or 4 years old) from three different centres located inside that city. In the section of the report that is devoted to analysis, additional information is presented that pertains to the comprehensive nature of the Teaching Strategies GOLD data. A non-random selection of fifty toddlers ranging in age from three to four years old who had filled out a consent form and submitted it were also included in the sample. The sample consisted of all twenty preschool teachers. In order to comply with the policies that governed the sharing of data in Program B, participants needed to sign consent forms before revealing any information about themselves. There were three of the youngsters who did not acquire any scores that were high enough to earn the GOLD classification for Teaching Strategies. In the section of the report that is dedicated to the examination of the data, you will find supplementary information that expands on the breadth of coverage provided by the Teaching Strategies GOLD data.

TOOLS

The outcomes of starting school at a young age. The extent to which the current capabilities of a child meet up to a standard that has been established, a set of norms, or a series of developmental benchmarks.

Teaching Strategies GOLD. A tool that is used to provide ongoing formative assessments to each child, and these evaluations are based on the observations made by the instructor with reference to the children's developmental progress.

DATA ANALYSIS

The findings of this study can be organised into a variety of different categories based on the characteristics of the children, the qualities of the teachers, the early learning results, the dose, and the evaluations of the classroom quality.

Characteristics and characteristics of children Both of these programmes gathered information regarding the children's ages, genders, and the races or ethnicities that they represented. While there were around 58% female children participating in Program A, there were only 38% female children participating in Program B. (table 1). While the average age of participants in Program A was somewhat greater than four years, the average age of participants in Program B was three years and nine months. In addition to this, Program B provided.

Table 1. The following table contains statistics describing the children who took part in Programs A and B during the 2019-2020 academic year (percent, unless otherwise noted)

Characteristic	Mean	Program A		Program B	
		Standard error	Mean	Standard error	
Female	58	0.04	38	0.05	
Age (months)	49	0.53	45	0.64	

Family income	-	-	Rs 11,337	Rs.849
Race/ethnicity				
Black	38	0.04	15	0.03
White	7	0.02	5	0.02
Indian	34	0.04	-	-
Other	22	0.03	80	0.04
Primary language				
English	-	-	68	0.04
Hindi	-	-	28	0.04
Other	-	-	5	0.02

English was the first language spoken by 68 percent of respondents, while Hindi was the primary language spoken by 28 percent; information on primary language and household income was also supplied (mean was Rs. 11,337). Through the Program A system, this data were inaccessible at any time.

Those qualities that make a great educator Both organisations were quite helpful in providing details on the qualifications of their respective instructors. The credentials of the teacher included a position as a lead teacher in preschool, a position as a teacher in preschool, a position as a lead teacher in infant toddler, a position as a teacher in infant toddler, a position as a director 1, and a position as a director 2. Eleven out of the twelve instructors who worked for the Program A were qualified to teach preschoolers at the lead level, and among the three of them, at least one director certification was held by each of them. Every single educator who worked in Program B had a director certification, and 18 of them also had a lead teacher certification for preschoolers. In total, there were 19 educators who possessed these certifications.

The outcomes of starting school at a young age. Early learning outcomes for children were found to include their growth in literacy, mathematics, and social-emotional development, as stated by the findings of the Teaching Strategies GOLD study.

It has been demonstrated that the Teaching Strategies GOLD scores are dependable and have a high degree of internal consistency across all three dimensions that are pertinent to the research objectives (literacy, mathematics, and social-emotional development³). Literacy has a Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.98, mathematics has a reliability coefficient of 0.97, and social-emotional development also has a reliability coefficient of 0.97. All of the inter-rater reliability indicators were determined to be higher than 90, which was the threshold that was set (Lambert, Kim, Taylor, & McGee, 2010). Each aspect of the evaluation receives a score from the teachers, which is based on a point system ranging from 0 (very poor) to 9 (very good) (high). The research team determined the overall average score by considering all of the items in each area (12 for reading, 7 for arithmetic, and 9 for social-emotional development). The number of items varied depending on the domain (12 for reading, 7 for arithmetic, and 9 for social-emotional development). Both the programme administrators and the teaching staff at both schools were given training on the Teaching Strategies GOLD curriculum. Both of these preschool programmes administer the Teaching Strategies GOLD exam on multiple occasions throughout the course of the academic year, and they have already submitted data for the evaluations that are scheduled to take place in the fall of 2019 and the spring of 2020 respectively. (Table 2).

Table 2. The following is an average representation of Programs A and B's performance on the Teaching Strategies GOLD assessment, which was administered in the fall and spring of 2019/20.

Program and domain	Fall		Spring		t-statistic for difference in means
	Mean	Standard error	Mean	Standard error	
Program A					
Literacy	3.39	0.1	4.15	0.14	5.07**
Math	3.83	0.11	4.43	0.15	3.90**
Social-emotional development	4.37	0.13	4.88	0.17	3.29*
Program B					
Literacy	2.64	0.16	3.86	0.17	11.94
Math	3.04	0.17	4.28	0.17	10.58*

Social-emotional development	4.38	0.17	5.64	0.15	10.98**
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Fig.1 scores on the Teaching Strategies GOLD assessment that were conducted in the autumn of 2019/20 and the spring of the following academic year for Programs A and B.

An investigation into the existing information regarding the effects of early education

Scores are given to users of Teaching Strategies GOLD on an item-by-item basis rather than on a domain-by-domain basis. This is because scoring is more accurate this way. Thirty percent of the children who are a part of Program A have all items scored in all domains for the autumn and spring Teaching Strategies GOLD tests, sixty-four percent have some things scored, and six percent have none. This information is based on the results of the tests that were administered. The total number of children used to calculate these percentages was fifty. Every sphere adheres to a format that is analogous to this one, and this is one of them (table 3). Tests for Teaching Strategies GOLD were administered twice a year in the fall and spring to a group of fifty children who were enrolled in Program B. Seventy-three percent of the children have all things scored in all domains, twenty-four percent have some, and three percent have none. None of those children are missing any items.

The research team conducted an analysis of missing data in order to address the question of whether or not the children who had scores were distinct from those children who had no scores. We used a t-test for continuous variables and a chi-squared test for categorical variables to compare the characteristics of the children who had all of the items to those of the children who had none of the items. The t-test was used for continuous variables, and the chi-squared test was used for categorical variables. The outcomes of these comparisons were assessed by looking at how they stacked up against one another. Each programme had two characteristics with significant differences between children with missing data and children with complete data: the children's age and the number of days they participated in the programme (in the case of Program A), and the children's primary language (in the case of Program B), and the number of days they participated in the programme (in the case of Program B). In each case, the children's primary language was significantly different between children with missing data and children with complete data (in the case of Program B). When the characteristics of children who owned part of the commodities were compared to those of children who owned all of the products, it was found that the same factors were significant in both groups of children.

Table 3. The number and percentage of children that participated in Programs A and B and received a Teaching Strategies GOLD score on either all items, some items, or none of the items during the autumn and spring evaluations in 2019/20.

Program and domain	All items		Some items		No items		Total	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
Program A								
Overall	20	30	30	64	9	6	50	100
Literacy	20	30	30	64	9	6	50	100
Math	20	36	30	58	9	6	50	100
Social- emotiona 1	20	36	30	58	9	6	50	100
Program B								
Overall	30	73	20	24	3	3	50	100
Literacy	30	75	20	23	3	3	50	100
Math	30	76	20	22	3	3	50	100
Social- emotiona 1	30	80	20	17	3	3	50	100

Source: Authors' analysis based on data from Programs A and B.

Fig.2 Programs A and B who achieved a Teaching Strategies GOLD score on all item.

After that, the research team applied a technique known as multiple imputation by chained equation, which is also known as sequential regression multivariate imputation in some circles. They were able to substitute missing data with simulated values using this strategy, which gave them 40 distinct value sets to choose from. Adjustments were made to the standard errors of the point estimates that were discovered through the analyses in order to account for the increased uncertainty that was brought about by the lack of data. This method was chosen because it does not require monotone missing data patterns, and it enables all other variables, including those that need to be imputed, to operate as explanatory variables. This was a major factor in our decision to utilize this method. Because of this, the approach was utilised. (Please refer to Lee and Carlin's (2010) article for a more in-depth description of the properties of the multiple imputation chained equation technique.) The research team conducted these estimations in order to raise the amount of faith that can be placed in the findings that were published in the study. As a result of these analyses, the level of trust can be increased. The capabilities of a typical administrator are far exceeded by those required for this operation.

Multiple imputations were performed on the data at the item level by the research team. Along with all of the other nonmissing items from the same domain that were gathered in the fall and the spring, the characteristics that were found to be significant in the analysis of missing data were included as predictor variables in these imputations. These imputations were performed on the data that was missing. Because seventy percent of the children who participated in Program A were absent from some items and, as a result, were absent from domain

scores, item scores were imputed in place of domain scores (which are calculated as the average of the item scores).

Compared to the 22–48 percent of youngsters who were missing each particular item, this represents a significant decrease. In the same manner, 10–21 percent of the children in Program B were missing each item, whereas 27 percent of the children were missing domain scores. In addition, because the analysis was carried out at the item level, the research team was able to include all of the other items in the domain as predictor variables. This was made possible because the study was carried out at the item level. This was carried out in accordance with the research that has been conducted, which recommends that imputation models make use of variables that have a high degree of correlation between them (Allison, 2020). There were twelve components that were imputed that pertained to reading, seven that pertained to mathematics, and nine that pertained to social-emotional development.

CONCLUSION

The practices of preschools in terms of early learning outcomes, classroom quality, and the amount of time children spend engaged in early childhood education are the primary focus of this inquiry. These procedures include data collecting and usage (for example, teacher-child interactions). This study aimed to evaluate the correlations between dose, classroom quality, and early learning outcomes as a means of better understanding those linkages. Previous studies have demonstrated a beneficial connection between the amount administered and the quality of the classroom environment as well as the early learning outcomes. It is likely that evaluations of children, teachers, and early childhood education programmes in general could be affected by data relevant to the aforementioned topics and fields.

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